
USE OF MOBILE TECHNOLOGY APPLICATION IN LIBRARIES

Dr. B. S. Padval¹ & Mr. Prashant Ashok Thorat²

¹Librarian, M. H. Shinde Mahavidyalaya, Tisangi.

²Research Scholar, Dep. of. Lib. & Inf. Sci. Shivaji University, Kolhapur.

Corresponding Author - Dr. B. S. Padval

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.7187751

Abstract:

This research topic focuses on the use of the application of mobile technology in libraries Basically most of the libraries are fully automated digital libraries and these libraries use mobile technology and this is essential because today there has been a huge explosion of information so that the use of mobile technology has increased so that the readers get the information they want right and quickly.

Key Terms: *Mobile Application, Digital Library, Library Services, SMS Services etc.*

Introduction:

Now a Day information and Communication technology is the most important part of the human life development the use of digital technology in higher education has attracted much interest in recent years. Students engage with campus life carrying highly sophisticated computing devices in their pockets. Frequently these students use these devices for a variety of purposes. Institutes of higher education are concerned that both their staff and students are digitally literate, in the manner of learning delivery or method of instruction. Mobile learning has been claimed as the future of learning and an examination of this claim leads to questions of how institutions are promoting mobile initiatives, what the mobile profile of their staff and students is, and whether their initiatives are progressing learning

technology. Applications (apps) are a fundamental feature of mobile devices and the volume and complexity of apps continues to increase unabated. Technological advances in recent years have been quickly adopted by many academic researchers. These technologies enable educators and researchers on desktop PCs to synchronies real time and large volumes of data from mobile apps. Mobile devices can be valuable in higher education for such activities as gathering and using information, accessing content, promoting communication.

Application of Mobile Phones:

The Wireless technology and mobile phones are becoming an integral part of everyday life and are changing the way one connects and interacts with the world. Mobile phones have wide variety of applications.

Mobile Library

Dictionary

Messaging

Messenger

WhatsApp

We chat

Instagram

Twitter

News Hunt

Email

Gmail

Face book

Adobe Acrobat

Excel

Power Point

Camera

Gallery

MX Player

Play Store

Google

Internet Explorer

Chrome

UC Browser

Drive

Digital Locker

Amazon

Flip kart

Mobile Banking

Cam Scanner Etc..

Following are some of the applications of mobile phones that we all use in our daily life:

- **Dictionary:** Dictionaries can be used to check spelling, to learn new words, to find or double-check the meaning of a word you encounter, or to find the right word to use.
- **Messaging:** Messaging is part of everyday life and critical to how stuff gets done. As human beings,

we're continuously sending and receiving information, and we're incredibly good at processing data to understand how to function in real time in the world around us. Yet, we take our sophisticated skills for granted.

- **Messenger:** Messenger is a **proprietary instant messaging app and platform.**

- **WhatsApp:** WhatsApp is better than text messaging because it's free of charge and more secure. Most customers prefer WhatsApp over texting due to its user interface and versatility.
- **WeChat:** WeChat provides text messaging, hold-to-talk voice messaging, broadcast (one-to-many) messaging, video conferencing, video games, sharing of photographs and videos and location sharing.
- **Instagram:** Instagram is a free social media app for sharing photos and videos with friends and followers.
- **Twitter:** Twitter is a micro blogging and social networking service owned by American company Twitter, Inc., on which users post and interact with messages known as "tweets". Registered users can post, like, and retweet tweets, while unregistered users only have a limited ability to read public tweets.
- **News Hunt:** News Hunt will send regular notifications to make you updated about breaking news or predicted news.
- **Email:** Electronic mail is a method of exchanging messages ("mail") between people using electronic devices.
- **Gmail:** Gmail is a free email service provided by Google.
- **Facebook:** Facebook is an online social media and social networking service.
- **Adobe Acrobat:** Adobe Acrobat is a family of application software and Web services developed by Adobe Inc. to view, create, manipulate, print and manage Portable Document Format (PDF) files.
- **Excel:** Microsoft Excel is a spreadsheet developed by Microsoft for Windows, macOS, Android and iOS. It features calculation or computation capabilities, graphing tools.
- **Power Point:** MS PowerPoint: is a program that is included in the Microsoft Office suite. It is used to make Custom animation Add photos, videos and sound effects Print presentations as handouts Embed YouTube videos presentations for personal and professional purposes.
- **Camera:** A camera is an optical instrument that captures a visual image and that use or personal and professional purposes.
- **Google / Internet Explorer / Chrome / UC Browser:** that is important web browser and that use searching information searching website educational purpose
- **Cam Scanner:** this devices to be used as image scanners. It allows users to 'scan' documents (by taking a photo with the device's camera) and share the photo as either a JPEG or PDF.
- By using the above application in the library as well as in our daily life we can complete our work faster and save our time by using this technology.

Mobile Library Services:

1. SMS Alert Service:

- To Send SMS to Collect the Requested Books.
- News and Events Reminder Service: This Service Sends Reminders to Patrons about

Important News, Exhibitions, Instruction, and Further More as a result taking place.

- New Title Announcement Examine.
- Reminder regarding Book is due in his / her Account; informing user about the exact fine.
- Concede the user about renewal of a book.
- Mobile library instruction.
- Multimedia borrowing notification service.

2. OPAC Service:

OPAC (Online Public Access Catalogue) Service to library user for get information about library collection which they require. Library user can search books, thesis and periodicals by keyword of title, author, publisher, ISBN/ISSN No., Subject and Accession number etc.

At anywhere of world through internet connection and get information about searched collection like status of books(available or issued) no. of copies and location (books stocked in which Institute library) and other bibliographical details.

3. Image Service:

The image services in library providing article, digitized photographs, diagrams, maps, photos of place of national significance.

4. Mobile Collections:

Second part substance contributor is collaborator through libraries to transport audio books, e-books, audio language courses, streaming music, films, images, and other multimedia that can be worn on mobile devices.

Advantages Mobile Technology:

- Save the time of the reader.

- Low Coast.
- Easy Communication
- Any time any place access to the information
- One time more than people access information.
- In receipt of alert on overdue books.
- In receipt of alert on outstanding fines.
- Receiving reminder to return library items that will be due soon.

Disadvantages of Mobile Technology:

- Expenditure
- Distraction during work
- Security and Privacy Issues
- Speed of access

Conclusion:

Today's Mobile technology is the largest and vital part of human life. It has rapidly changed the way of seeking and dissemination information. It is clear from the study that how mobile phone is useful to preparation of classroom teaching and research work. This study helps the librarian in planning and developing modern mobile technology application in providing better modern services to the library users.

Reference:

1. <http://www.libsuccess.org/index.php?title=M-Libraries/> (accessed on 03.09.2022).
2. World cat. <http://www.worldcat.org/mobile/> (accessed on 03.09.2022).
3. What mobile services does your library offer? Library Connect, 2009, 7(4), 8. <http://libraryconnectarchive.elsevier.com/1cn/0704/1cn070407.html/> (Accessed on 03.09.2022).

4. M-Libraries.(2012).Retrieved from<http://libsucces.org/index.php?title=M-Libraries>. (Accessed on 03.09.2022).
5. Hanson, W. Cody. (2011). Libraries and Mobile Services. American Libraries Magazine, Retrieved from, <http://americanlibrariesmagazine.org/columns/dispatches-field/libraries-and-mobile-services>. (Accessed on 03.09.2022).
6. DINESH, R., .ARUN PRAVIN, S., ARAVINDHAN, M., & RAJESWARI, D. (2015). LIBRARY ACCESS SYSTEM SMARTPHONE APPLICATION USING ANDROID. International Journal of Computer Science and Mobile Computing, 4(4), 142-149.
7. Dr. K. Kumar. Application of Mobile Technology among Engineering College Library users: A Study. Community of Knowledge.
8. Saxena, A., &Yadav, R. (2013). IMPACT OF MOBILE TECHNOLOGY ON LIBRARIES: A DESCRIPTIVE STUDY. International Journal of Digital Library Services, 3(4), 1-58.
9. Suthar, A. A. (2013). USING MOBILE TECHNOLOGY TO DELIVER EFFECTIVE LIBRARY SERVICES. Asian Journal of Library and Information, 5(3), 72-75.
10. Sharma, D. (2014). Application of Mobile Technology in Library Services: An Overview. International Journal of Information Technology and Library Science, 3(2), 17-24. (Accessed on 04.09.2022). from <http://www.ripublication.com>
11. Mandale S. R. and Kharade V.V, (2014), Use of Cloud Computing in library and information Science field; National conference on Changing Trends in Academic Libraries and Librarianship in Digital Environment; 25-26-Feb,2014;Kolhapur:Shivaji University; p.p.359.362.
12. Hase, V. L., & Gaikwad, M. N. (2021). Online Databases Backbone for Teaching and Research: Case Study of Rajarambapu Institute of Technology, affiliated to Shivaji University, Kolhapur, Maharashtra (India).from<https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/6873/>
13. https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=en&user=hYAbHG8AAAAJ&citation_for_view=hYAbHG8AAAAJ:roLk4NBRz8UC